

An allegorical fiction masterpiece

A book review of Wild Wise Weird

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[Wild Wise Weird](#) by Quan-Hoang Vuong is a delightful anthology that brings to life the whimsical world of a wise, solitary Kingfisher navigating a vibrant bird village. Each story blends humor and thoughtful commentary, creating a journey filled with both charm and valuable insight. Through Kingfisher's interactions with his fellow birds, I am taken to reflect on universal humanistic values like justice, honesty, responsibility, freedom, community, and the bonds between humans and nature. This feeling of timelessness can hardly be found if not reading other classics, like [Animal Farm](#), [The Little Prince](#), [Laugh or Lament](#), [Alice's Adventures in Wonderland](#), etc.

When compared with *Animal Farm*, I can see both similarities and differences between the two books. For similarities, the two books feature animals as central characters to convey their messages and satire of human society. However, unlike *Animal Farm*, which is written as a single continuous narrative, *Wild Wise Weird* is written as a collection of short stories, which is similar to the approach in *Laugh or Lament*.

While *Animal Farm* and *Laugh or Lament* have more serious and darker tone, reflecting the grim realities of political and social issues, like oppression in totalitarian regimes, economic inequalities, and bureaucratic absurdities, *Wild Wise Weird* is more whimsical and humorous, reflecting the absurdity in various human traits and societal norms. Perhaps the content of *Wild Wise Weird* often revolves around the everyday lives and moral dilemmas of characters in the bird village, making

it light-hearted, even when addressing serious topics.

All in all, I think the themes and stories are relevant for a wide range of readers in different generations. It is even suitable for use as a bedtime story for kids. Most importantly, after reading the book, I know why other readers call it "[classic](#)" and "[masterpiece](#)". A must-read for anyone looking for joyful and thought-provoking moments.

References

Vuong, Q. H. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6/>